

CREATIVE THINKING IN PRESCHOOL SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. *The development of creativity in each individual is individual. The socialization of education is a systemic factor in the development of creativity. The first signs of creativity are unique to each person. However, various prohibitions and social stereotypes in the environment in which he grows up, is brought up and educated lead to the blocking of creative activity. For the development of creativity in children, it is necessary to release them from psychological pressures and give a positive impetus.*

Keywords: *preschool, education, upbringing, thinking, creativity, motivation, ability.*

ТВОРЧЕСКОЕ МЫШЛЕНИЕ В ДОШКОЛЬНОМ СОЦИАЛЬНО-ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОМ АСПЕКТЕ РАЗВИТИЯ

Аннотация. *Развитие творческих способностей у каждого человека индивидуально. Социализация образования является системным фактором развития творчества. Первые признаки творчества уникальны для каждого человека. Однако различные запреты и социальные стереотипы в среде, в которой он растет, воспитывается и воспитывается, приводят к блокированию творческой деятельности. Для развития творчества у детей необходимо освободить их от психологического давления и дать положительный импульс.*

Ключевые слова: *дошкольное образование, образование, воспитание, мышление, творчество, мотивация, способности.*

INTRODUCTION

The study of human thinking is one of the main problems in psychology, it is a very complex process and therefore requires constant research. Thinking is done in concepts and imaginations, and the main form of understanding is thinking and reasoning.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In preschool children, the areas of learning begin first, and then the inner personal life in the direction of emotional motivation. It goes from figurative to symbolic in its development in one direction or another. Imagery refers to children's ability to create, modify, and move different images, and symbolism refers to children's ability to work with a system of signs (mathematical, linguistic, logical, etc.). The creative process begins at a pre-school age. Creativity is mainly reflected in children's design games, technical and artistic creativity. During this time, the buds begin to show signs of development. In cognitive processes, a synthesis of internal and external movements occurs. In thinking, however, practical problems are manifested as the integration of methods of work into a single general process.

RESULTS

On this basis, the human intellect is formed and developed. In the preschool period, imagination, thinking, and speech are generalized. This is an indication that inner speech is emerging as a factor in thinking in children of this age. The synthesis of cognitive processes is based on the complete mastery of the child's native language. At this stage, the process of speech

formation begins. In the process of speech-based upbringing, the child acquires elementary moral norms and rules. These norms and rules govern child's morality.

There are different relationships between the child and those around him, and these relationships are based on different motives. All of this organizes a child's individuality, transforming him or her into a person who differs from other children not only in intellect but also in moral motivation.

Preschoolers are the pinnacle of personal development, the realization of their own personal qualities, abilities, successes and failures, and a sense of self-awareness.

The problem of the individual and his formation is wide-ranging, covering several fronts. Here we analyze the research on the problem of the individual and his formation.

DISCUSSION

It links the development of an individual to the systematic management of his activities, and on this basis shows the manifestations of management.

1. Manage the smooth continuity of development. This includes the process, state, and characteristics that control the dynamics of the activity.

2. Incentive management. Includes all the motivational processes, situations, and characteristics that drive the activity process.

3. Flexible management. Provides a balance between an individual's activities and their results.

4. Effective management. It connects the cognitive scheme with the system of motor skills, type and level of ability, perception, imagination, thinking and speech.

5. Structural qualities. Personality traits.

CONCLUSIONS

Usually, any process of thinking is caused by surprise, astonishment and, as a result, various questions. Many parents and some educators, when children ask too many questions, joke, "Don't be too secretive," "Where did you learn such things?" As a result, the child tries to understand the outside world as he knows it. But some passive and shy kids don't ask any questions. Such children should be asked questions by adults during various activities and trips, and thus activate them.

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